

Book Review

ECOLOGIA E CONSERVAÇÃO DE ECOSSISTEMAS AQUÁTICOS DO SUL DO BRASIL

Organizadores

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This book contributes to filling the enormous gap in the information on aquatic ecosystems in southern Brazil. This region is a continental reference regarding the composition, structure, and function of its aquatic ecosystems. In addition, it can help to put together the harsh puzzle that makes up the relationships between man, water

resources, and biodiversity conservation. The publication is open access and carefully edited in Portuguese by the Pró-Pampa Institute, founded in 2006 with headquarters in Pelotas, whose main purpose is to develop and participate in actions aimed at biodiversity conservation. The edition is based on the BAPs, follows homogeneous criteria, and the different chapters and the work have been submitted for peer review.

The book is organized into four sections: the physiology of aquatic crustaceans in the region, the ecology of populations and communities, the ecology of the landscape and ecosystems, and the conservation and the public policies, preceded by an introductory chapter. Note that the plan for the work does not intend to cover all areas of the aquatic ecosystems of Rio Grande do Sul, a task that would be impossible because of the enormous

amount of work that still needs to be done. Instead, the book succeeds in its main achievement, which is the international presentation of the hydrobiological heritage of the region, and it provides an extensive and relevant bibliographic review in each of the chapters of the different sections. The authors and editors count on the interest of each of the contributions, which will undoubtedly trigger an explosion of research on the aquatic ecosystems of southern Brazil by other Brazilian scientists and the rest of the world.

The book begins with a special chapter that dedicates an affectionate autobiographical tribute to Professor Maximiano Pinheiro Cirne, an illustrious ornithologist from the region who sadly died during gestation.

The remainder of this work can be read in several ways.

- From beginning to end, as the chapters progress.
- Discriminating by section or section according to the reader's specialty.
- "Diagonally," extracting from the different chapters the descriptions of the areas of study considered.
- Under cross-cutting themes in different sections, which we will follow here to review every chapter.

If the reader chooses to discriminate by section, I recommend reading Chapters 1, 10, 11, 12, 14, 16, and 17 if interested in revising holistic approaches to address aspects of regional limnology, classification, conservation status, environmental impacts, and threats, with a final emphasis on urban wetlands. In turn, readers who love crustaceans and other aquatic invertebrates enjoy reading chapters 2, 3, 4, 7, and 8. For those interested in the basic and applied aspects of aquatic vegetation, I recommend reading chapters 5, 6, 8, 10, and 11. Finally, for those who are interested mainly in fish, but also in other vertebrates, Chapters 7, 9, 13, and 15 are must-read.

One strength of the book is its consideration of aquatic ecosystems in indigenous populations, especially in Chapter 1.

Also noteworthy is the technical approach of several chapters, such as the one dedicated to aquatic macrophytes with the potential for the remediation of polluted aquatic environments, the impact of wetland fragmentation on a passerine population, the conservation of reed beds, the problems of environmental degradation in urban wetlands, and the regional assessment of the environmental pressure of roads on the streams of Rio Grande do Sul, among others. Professional consulting work supports the corresponding chapters by the authors, reconciling scientific quality with applied interests.

Perhaps the most fascinating and masterful chapter to propose solutions is the one that deals with basic guidelines for the environmental authorization of projects in areas of confirmed or potential presence of annual fish of the Rivulidae family in the municipality of Pelotas, which is another product of the environmental consulting contracts of the Pró-Pampa Institute.

Whether one reads with the interest of a specialist or a generalist, the book leaves a bitter sensation because of the interest in its content and, the hunger

to know more about the limnology of Rio Grande do Sul, recalling the Spanish saying that goes: “Eat and scratch, everything is beginning.” Going through the pages of any chapter awakens the inspiration of new tasks to undertake and perspectives to adopt, taxonomic and bibliographic databases, exploration projects to delve into the region, experiments to delve into several of the topics or impulses to contribute to the grain of sand to the search for solutions to the disturbing challenges posed by the conservation of aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity in southern Brazil. The greatest “danger” of the book is that temptation, which is also its greatest attraction, will seduce the reader.

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Book Announcement

Front cover

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Sample Figure. A. *D. magna* publications by year; black bars for basic science, open bars for ecotoxicology. Figure B. The first illustration of *D. magna* from Schäffer's (1755) book on freshwater organisms.

Daphnia magna by Winfried Lampert
 Winfried Lampert's long-awaited monograph about *Daphnia magna* is now available at Amazon (just search "Daphnia magna by Winfried Lampert") – 499 pages – hardcover for \$24 (US)
ISBN: 9798305527681

Winfried Lampert (1941-2021) was one of the foremost experts on the ecology and evolutionary biology of the genus *Daphnia*, and, as Director at the Max Planck Institute for Limnology in Plön,

Germany (1984 to retirement in 2006), led a famous zooplankton research group, primarily focused on *Daphnia*. He was the recipient of numerous recognitions including the SIL Nauman-Thienemann Medal and ASLO Redfield Award. After retirement, he continued to be active in *Daphnia* research, including writing this remarkable book about *Daphnia magna* as an important ecological, eco-genomic and ecotoxicological model organism. The book's extensive coverage includes chapters on *History of discovery, Systematics/Biogeography, Morphology, Biochemistry, Reproduction, Population Genetics, Feeding, Metabolism, Growth, Development, Life History, Population Dynamics and Behavior*. The book

is thoroughly illustrated with figures newly redrawn from the primary literature. Winfried Lampert completed drafting the book just before his untimely death from cancer in 2021, and his daughter and son, both successful university scientists, completed bring the book to publication this year. Published at cost for US\$24, it is an exceptional bargain worthy of a place on every freshwater plankton biologist's bookshelf.

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